

A Commentary on the Significance of the Development of the Decorative Visor Design on the Series 2 Imitative Owls of Andragoras.

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This working paper examines the significance of the development of the closed loop, or volute end termination on the decorative visor of Athena's helmet, which is found exclusively on the Series 2 imitative Athenian coinage of Andragoras of Parthia. It places this development in the context of similar developments in the Athenian prototype (Athenian Heterogeneous Group C) to conclude that the imitative coinage was struck in the mid-3rd century BC, dispelling the notion of previous scholars that it dates to the 4th century BC.

In a study¹ of the imitative Athenian coinage previously attributed to Baktria, in which I argued the case for reattribution to the satrapy of Andragoras of Parthia, I noted three important developments in the transition from the earliest (Series 1) to the latest (Series 2) of the imitative Athenian owls. Initially Series 2 maintained the the same Athenian imitative iconography of Series 1. It commenced with the same mint controls as the last of the Series 1, establishing continuity between the two series. However, in the transition from Series 1 to Series 2, the 12 o'clock die adjustment and square reverse dies, manifest by a square incuse design on Series 1 (Figure 1a) were altered to a 6 o'clock die adjustment accompanied by the use of cylindrical dies, resulting in a flat circular reverse (Figure 1b) that on some specimens left a partial circular incuse edge (Figure 2a). After these changes in coin fabric, in the course of the mintage of Series 2 the the depiction of the decorative visor on Athena's helmet changed on all but the fractional denominations. Due to space limitations, in the original article detailing the study, the exposition of the full nature and significance of this development was curtailed. This working note expands on that presented in the original article.² It highlights the chronological significance of this development in the context of competing theories of the origin of the coinage.

The most notable aspect in the evolution of the helmeted Athena head on the imitative owls of Series 2 was the addition of a closed circular loop, or volute, positioned above the ear, defining the hinge point at the inner end of decorative visor on the leading edge of Athena's helmet (Figures 1b and 2b).³ This iconographic detail is absent on all other imitative Athenian coinage regardless of geography or chronology. Rather, the inner end of the visor design is depicted by two parallel, or weakly convergent lines with an open end (Figures 1a and 2a), rather than a closed circular loop, or volute, above Athena's ear. The open-ended termination of the decorative visor is consistent with the Athenian prototype pi-style coinage. Furthermore, it is identical to that of all Athenian coinage depicting Athena's helmeted head from the 6th century BC down to the 3rd century BC. However, by the 2nd century BC, the closed loop, volute termination of the visor was firmly established on the Athenian Symbol tetradrachms (196-168 BC) from which it developed further into a prominent circular boss on the Athenian New Style tetradrachms (168-42 BC).⁴ This raises the question as to the origin

¹ Taylor (2019): 53-54.

² This working paper is a small component in a broader study by the author of the phenomenon of mid-3rd century BC imitative coinage produced in several of the eastern provinces in the Seleukid realm.

³ Taylor (2019): 53 for an outline of this development on the imitative Athenian and later coinage of Andragoras.

⁴ Sverdrup and Schlyter (2013): fig. 1.

of the depiction of the closed loop termination of the visor on both the Athenian coinage and the Series 2 imitative Athenian coinage. In considering this, it is important to remember that the ornate Attic helmet depicted on the coinage of Athens was largely an artistic construct loosely based on real helmets.⁵ A survey of vase art and numismatic art depicting figures in Attic helmets sees the first depiction of the volute closed end decorative visor emerge in the 3rd century BC, then to become a frequently encountered design motif on depictions of what are loosely described as Attic style helmets during the balance of the Hellenistic era, and continuing into Roman times.

Figure 1. Imitative Athenian tetradrachms attributed to Andragoras, satrap of Parthia.⁶

Figure 2. Andragoras Series 2 didrachms illustrating visor hinge development.⁷

On Athenian owls prior to the 2nd century BC, the closed loop termination has only been identified on the tetradrachms of Athenian Heterogeneous Groups B and C, detailed and illustrated by Nicolet-Pierre and Kroll.⁸ Originally considered to be imitations from an uncertain mint in mainland Greece, they are now believed to represent Athenian produced civic coinage⁹ dating to the periods *c.* 270-260 BC (Group C) and 250-225 BC (Group B).¹⁰ A notable aspect of the Heterogeneous Group C tetradrachms is that they departed from prior Athenian issues not only in the depiction of the visor termination on the helmet, but also in

⁵ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Attic_helmet (accessed 26 July 2020).

⁶ Fig. 1(a) Roma Numismatics XIV, lot 344; Fig. 1(b) Roma Numismatics E-Sale 44, lot 312.

⁷ Coins from the author's collection.

⁸ Nicolet-Pierre and Kroll (1990): 14-16, pls.4-5.

⁹ Kroll (2013): 37-38.

¹⁰ Dating defined on the basis of their earliest occurrence of Athenian Heterogeneous Group C in the Krčedin 1953 Hoard (*CH* 9, 166) that closed *c.* 270-260 BC and the Phayttos 1918 Hoard (*IGCH* 159) that closed *c.* 260 BC. The dates of these hoards is subject to some uncertainty, but it is clear that based on the hoard data presented by Nicolet-Pierre and Kroll (1990), that Group C precedes Group B. Group C dates to the 2nd quarter of the 3rd century BC, while Group B is most likely of the third century BC. As such, Athenian Heterogeneous Groups B and C are precursors to the Athenian Symbol Series (196-168 BC) and subsequently the New Style Athenian coinage (168-42 BC).

the adjustment of the die axes and most notably in the use of cylindrical dies in contrast to the square dies of previous issues.¹¹ Similar changes are observed in the transition from Series 1 to Series 2 in the imitative owls of Andragoras.¹² This is either a truly remarkable coincidence, or the Athenian Heterogeneous Group C influenced the development of Series 2 in the Parthian satrapy of Andragoras.

The introduction of the closed loop, or volute end termination of the decorative visor in the later part of Series 2 was not carried over to fractional denominations, probably due to the difficulty of detailing this element on small diameter dies.¹³ However, once established on the larger denominations of Series 2 it was maintained on all the later series that involved the depiction of an Attic helmet (Series 3 and 7)¹⁴ including the issues of Sophytes (Series 8) on which an Attic style helmet with cheek guards sits on a male head.¹⁵ Sustained through a sequence of issues, from the hands of many engravers, the introduction of the closed loop termination of the decorative visor on Series 2 was most certainly a conscious decision, rather than a die engraver's stylistic preference. Most plausibly this decision was influenced by the similar development on an Athenian prototype; the Heterogeneous Group C of the second quarter of the 3rd century BC. If so, then Series 2 must post-date this development on the Athenian coinage. This strengthens the argument for the dating of Series 2 to the middle of the 3rd century BC (and therefore the proposed association with the satrapy of Andragoras in Parthia). Certainly, the closed loop, or volute termination on the decorative visor argues strongly against the hypothesis that this imitative Athenian coinage originated in the 4th century BC.¹⁶

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¹¹ Nicolet-Pierre and Kroll (1990): 20.

¹² Taylor (2019): 53.

¹³ Taylor (2019): 53.

¹⁴ Taylor (2019): 54, 58-60.

¹⁵ Taylor (2019): 59-61.

¹⁶ Mitchiner (1975): 9; Nicolet-Pierre and Amandry (1990); Bopearachchi (1996); Bopearachchi(1998); Bordeaux and Bopearachchi (2018).

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